

Characterization of silicon tunnel field effect transistor based on charge plasma

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the proposed paper is an analytical model and realization of the characteristics for tunnel field-effect transistor (TFET) based on charge plasma (CP). One of the most applications of the TFET device which operates based on CP technique is the biosensor. CP-TFET is to be used as an effective device to detect the uncharged molecules of the bio-sample solution. Charge plasma is one of some techniques that recently invited to induce charge carriers inside the devices. In this proposed paper we use a high work function in the source ($\phi=5.93$ eV) to induce hole charges and we use a lower work function in drain ($\phi=3.90$ eV) to induce electron charges. Many electrical characterizations in this paper are considered to study the performance of this device like a current drain (ID) versus voltage gate (Vgs), I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio, threshold voltage (VT) transconductance (gm), and sub-threshold swing (SS). The signification of this paper comes into view enhancement the performance of the device. Results show that high dielectric (K=12), oxide thickness ($T_{ox}=1$ nm), channel length ($L_{ch}=42$ nm), and higher work function for the gate ($\phi=4.5$ eV) tend to best charge plasma silicon tunnel field-effect transistor characterization.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Charge plasma and electrostatic techniques are recently devised techniques to provocation the virtual doping inside the device [1], [2]. In the charge plasma technique, the charge carriers are motivated within the materials by employing different work functions on the drain and source regions, whereas in the electrostatic technique, the charge carriers are motivated within the materials by employing external bias [3], [4]. The tunnel field-effect transistor (TFET) device is vastly studied within the containing the virtual doping techniques [5]-[7]. TFET can be regarded as a promising alternative device of metal-oxide-semiconductors field effect transistor (MOSFET) to overcome the imperfection of short channel effects and betterment the characteristics of the device such as high I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio, low OFF-current state lower subthreshold slope and minimize the power consumption [8]-[11]. The operating mechanism of TFET is based on the band-to-band tunneling phenomenon, while in MOSFET, the operating mechanism is based on the thermionic emission technique [12]-[14]. Besides all these advantages, but TFET is still suffering from some problems and facing challenges like low ON-current state, ambipolar behavior (conduction of current when the gate bias is negative), and higher parasitic capacitances [15]-[18].

One of the most applications of the charge plasma tunnel field-effect transistor (CP-TFET) is the biosensor device which operates based on charge plasma technique [19]. There are other types of biosensors

device that depends on the ion-sensitive field-effect transistor (ISFET) [20]. ISFET operates on fundamental the presence of ions in the bio-sample solution below the dielectric gate, but ISFET cannot detect the uncharged molecules for any bio-sample, so this can be considered as limiters of ISFET [19]. While CP-TFET has been verified to be used as an effective device to detect the uncharged molecules of the bio-sample solution [21], [22]. Also, another type of FET biosensor is the dielectric modulated device has named DM-FET biosensor and DM-TFET which have higher sensitivity for bio-sample [23], [24].

This paper overcomes the problem of the detect uncharged molecules and precision of the sensitivity, by collecting all the beneficial features of the dielectric modulated (DM) biosensor, charge plasma conception and TFET device, the DM CP-TFET biosensor has been an ongoing device and its better performance as compared with other types of biosensor [25]-[27]. So, this proposed paper aims to realize and study the characteristics of TFET device that depend on the CP technique, and the signification of the work comes into view enhancement the performance of the device (sub threshold slop and I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio) which used as a biosensor applications.

2. DEVICE STRUCTURE AND PARAMETERS

The substructure of the device, siliconcharge plasma tunnel field-effect transistor (CP-TFET) is shown as in Figure 1. The source and drain regions are established on the intrinsic body by prober metal work function. “P+” source is implanted by ($\phi_S=5.93$ eV) and “N+” drain is implanted by ($\phi_D =3.9$ eV). The gate regions are established on SiO2 by different metal work functions. Gate1 and Gate2 are implanted by ($\phi =3.9$ eV), Gate3, and Gate4 ($\phi =4.0$ eV). The structure of the device is making the concentrations distribution electron and hole are available regular at source and drain electrode, which make better control and a great ON current-state [28]-[30]. The concentration of substrate region (body) is $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ which represents the silicon intrinsic and the length of the channel is 43 nm. Oxide layer thickness (SiO2) under the gate is 3 nm and the length of the gate under lap region (dielectric) or space length is 7 nm, and the applied voltage on the drain terminal (Vd) is 0.5 V.

In this article, we study and investigate the important electrical parameter (performance) for the device such as I_{ON} , I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio, sub-threshold slope (SS), the threshold voltage (VT) and transconductance (gm). The performance of the device was observed by varying many factors for the device such as different dielectric constant (under lap region(K)), oxide layer thickness (T_{OX}), and channel length (LCh) [31], [32].

Figure 1. Schematic structure of a CP-TFET

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation results are taken by using the Technology Computer Aided Design (TCAD) tool. The gate voltage (V_{GS}) is plotted against both drain current (I_{ON}) and transconductance (gm) in Figure 2 and Figure 3 at $K=1,2,4,8$, and 12). In Figure 2 is the effect of dielectric constant in drain current, wherein the (I_{ON}) increases when (K) increases and so on in Figure 3 of the (gm).

The relation between dielectric constant (k) versus the ratio of (I_{ON}/I_{OFF}) and subthreshold slope (SS) are plotted in Figure 4, which shows the increase of (K) led to an increase in the I_{ON}/I_{OFF} , while the opposite occurs in (SS), where increasing of (K), result in (SS) will decrease. Also, can be found the intersection point between them in about 5.2 of (K). The drain current and transconductance are plotted against voltage gate with a different thickness of $T_{OX} = (1,2,3, \text{ and } 4)$ as shown in Figures 5 and 6 respectively. The plots validate the performance of the device, at decreasing of the (T_{OX}), the I_D current and gm will be increasing. That’s mean the proportional is reverse between (I_D and gm) with (T_{OX}).

Figure 2. $I_D(I_{ON})$ versus voltage gate (V_{GS}) at varying (K)

Figure 3. Transconductance (g_m) versus voltage gate at varying (K)

Figure 4. I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio and (SS) versus different dielectric constant of (k)

Figure 5. $I_D(I_{ON})$ versus voltage gate (V_{GS}) at varying (Tox)

The relation between thickness material (T_{OX}) of (SiO₂) versus the ratio of I_{ON}/I_{OFF} and (SS) are plotted in Figure 7, which shows the minimum value of I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio (1.1×10^6) with $V_D = 0.5$ V was gotten at $T_{OX} = (1$ and $2)$ nm, but at $T_{OX} = 3$ nm, the I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio began increasing until reached to a maximum value (1.3×10^9) at $T_{OX} = 4$ nm. While occurs opposite in (SS), where the minimum value of $T_{OX} = 1$ nm at the same value of $V_D = 0.5$ V, we obtained the worse case of SS characteristics (84.19 mV/dec), but after that, when the value of T_{OX} began increasing, the value of SS became decreasing until reached to the best value of SS characteristics (63.26 mV/dec). Also, we can find the intersection point between them in about 3.7 of (T_{OX}).

Figure 6. Transconductance (gm) versus voltage gate at varying (T_{OX})

Figure 7. I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio and (SS) versus different thickness constant of (T_{OX})

The three parameters (work function, channel length and oxide thickness) are taken to investigation the characteristics of the charge plasma tunnel field-effect transistor (CP-TFET) device, like threshold voltage (V_t), I_{ON} current, I_{OFF} current, I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio, subthreshold slop (SS) and transconductance (gm). We set the work function of (gate1 and gate2) at fixed value (3.9 eV), channel length at fixed value (43 nm) and oxide thickness at fixed value (3 nm). While the work function of (gate3 and gate4) are set at variable value (4.5, 4.3, 4.1, and 3.9) eV. All the electrical characteristic of the device was obtained at $V_D = 0.5$ V, dielectric constant (K) = 12 and temperature degree of device at 300 K as shown as in Table 1.

The relation between channel length (L_{ch}) versus the ratio of (I_{ON}/I_{OFF}) and subthreshold slope (SS) are plotted in Figure 8, which shows the increase of (L_{ch}) led to decreasing in the I_{ON}/I_{OFF} , while the opposite occurs in (SS), where increasing of (L_{ch}), will result of decreasing in (SS).

Table 1. Electrical characteristic of CP-TFET ($k=12$ and $V_D=0.5$ V)

Work Function (Gate3+Gate4) (eV)	Channel Length (nm)	T_{OX} (nm)	V_t (V)	I_{ON} (A)	I_{OFF} (A)	I_{ON}/I_{OFF}	SS mmmV/dec	Gm u/S	Work Function (Gate1+Gate2) (eV)
4.5	43	3	0.954	1.52×10^{-8}	3.43×10^{-18}	$4.4 \times 10^{+9}$	33.84	0.050	3.9
4.3	43	3	0.954	1.53×10^{-8}	2.07×10^{-17}	$7.4 \times 10^{+8}$	50.75	0.051	3.9
4.1	43	3	0.954	1.54×10^{-8}	$3.9.87 \times 10^{-17}$	$1.5 \times 10^{+8}$	59.90	0.052	3.9

Figure 8. I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio and (SS) versus different thickness constant of (Lch)

4. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have been taken many factors to study and analyze the characteristics of silicon tunnel field-effect transistors based on charge plasma. The performance of the charge plasma tunnel field-effect transistor (CP-TFET) device studies and investigated through this paper. By using plasma technique concept based on TFET structure. A dual-gate metal structure and gate under lap region is proposed to enhancement the characteristic of the device. By simulation study, the CP-TFET device shows making better performance for $I_{ON}=1.5\times 10^{-8}$ A at (K=12, Lch=43 nm and $T_{OX}=3$ nm), $I_{ON}/I_{OFF}=1.3\times 10^9$ at (K=12, Lch=43 nm and $T_{OX}=4$ nm), and sub threshold slop SS=33.84 mV/dec at (K=12, work function for gate3 and gate4=4.5 eV).

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